

Exploring biosurfactant recovery using dialysis process at lab and pilot scale from corn steep water

A. Martínez-Arcos^{*,**}, N. Russo-Martínez^{*,**}, J.M. Cruz^{*,**}, B. Pérez-Cid^{*,**,*}, A.B. Moldes^{*,**}, X. Vecino^{*,**}

* Departamento de Enxeñaría Química, Escola de Enxeñaría Industrial, Universidade de Vigo, Campus As Lagoas-Marcosende, 36310 Vigo, España.

(E-mail: andrea.martinez.arcos@uvigo.gal; nicolasmauricio.russo@uvigo.gal; jmcruz@uvigo.gal; amoldes@uvigo.gal; xanel.vecino@uvigo.gal)

** CINTECX, Universidade de Vigo, EQ10, Campus As Lagoas-Marcosende, 36310 Vigo, España.

*** Departamento de Química Analítica e Alimentaria, Facultade de Química, Universidade de Vigo, Campus As Lagoas-Marcosende, 36310 Vigo, España.

(E-mail: benita@uvigo.gal)

Abstract

Dialysis process stands out as methods for concentrating, recovering, and purifying biomolecules based on their size and molecular mass. Dialysis operates through a diffusion and transport mechanism, whereby solutes migrate from a higher concentration region on one side of a semi-permeable membrane (the feed side) to a lower concentration region on the other side (the permeate side). On the other hand, corn steep water (CSW) is an agro-industrial stream derived from the corn wet-milling industry. CSW can be used as a direct source of extracellular and cell-linked biosurfactants, which are naturally produced through the spontaneous fermentation of corn during the steeping process. Therefore, in this work dialysis processes at lab and pilot scale have been used for the recovery of extracellular biosurfactants from CSW. Experiments at lab-scale were carried out with regenerated cellulose tubing dialysis membranes, and for pilot-scale was used a Diffusion Dialysis Lab Unit (Model AP-L05) from Mech-Chem (USA). Centrifugated CSW was dialyzed with Milli-Q water solution during 48h (lab-scale) or 72h (pilot-scale in closed system) at 4°C. The surfactant capacity, elemental analysis and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy analysis (FTIR) of the biosurfactant extracts were evaluated. Results show that it is possible to increase the Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) of the dialysis process from a TRL 1-3 to 4-6, this implies that the volume of CSW treated is increased at least 30 times, compared to the maximum volume treated at lab-scale in tubing membranes, without losing the surfactant capacity of the biosurfactant extract.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Biorefinery; corn stream; membrane technology; pilot-scale; surface-active compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Corn steep water (CSW) is a liquid residue derived from the wet milling process of corn, rich in nutrients such as sugars, amino acids, vitamins, lipids, minerals and other compounds. It is primarily used in fermentations, animal feed production due to its nutritional properties, and for agricultural as a potential biofertilizer (Taiwo and Musonge, 2024). Additionally, CSW can be used as a direct source of both cell-linked and extracellular biosurfactants (Vecino et al., 2014, 2015, 2023; López-Prieto et al., 2021). In this sense, biosurfactants are secondary metabolites produced by specific bacteria that are of great interest because they can replace chemical surfactants in certain formulations that are more sustainable, biocompatible and biodegradable (Singh et al., 2019). Consequently, the global market for biosurfactants was estimated at US\$7.0 Billion in 2023 and is projected to reach US\$10.2 Billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 5.5% from 2023 to 2030 (Research And Markets, 2020).

In the case of CSW, extracellular biosurfactants are typically recovered through liquid-liquid extraction processes using organic solvents, while cell-linked biosurfactants are extracted by solid-liquid extraction with buffer solutions such as phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Driven by the need to explore innovative and more environmentally friendly alternatives that avoid the use of organic solvents, the idea of applying membrane technology for the recovery of extracellular biosurfactants from CSW emerged, specifically through dialysis processes. In this context, the ATEMBIO project aims to apply the dialysis process for recovering these biosurfactants from CSW, with the goal of

advancing the TRL of the technology from the lab-scale (1-3) to the pilot-scale (4-6) and subsequently showing a comparative study of biosurfactant extracts obtained at both scales.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CSW was provided by FeedStimulants company (Lot No. CSL-0003-1217), diluted up to 50 g/L and centrifuged for solids removal (5000 rpm, 30 min, 4°C) (Martínez-Arcos et al., 2024). The centrifuged CSW was subjected to a lab-scale and pilot-scale dialysis processes as shown in **Figure 1**. On the one hand, lab-scale dialysis process was carried out with 6-8 kDa tubing cellulose dialysis membranes (around 88 cm² each bag) at 4°C for 48 hours, following the patent ES 2 931 088 B2 (Vecino et al., 2024). On the other hand, pilot-scale dialysis process was performed using a Diffusion Dialysis (DD) unit (Model AP-L05), manufactured by Mech-Chem (USA), equipped with 8 regenerated cellulose membrane sheets (6-8 kDa), with a total surface area of 929 cm². In this case, centrifuged CSW was pumped to the DD unit at 0.56 L/h·m² and counter current was pumped Milli-Q water at 1.12 L/h·m² during 27 cycles (closed system).

a)

b)

Figure 1. Experimental set-up of dialysis process for biosurfactant recovery at a) lab-scale and b) pilot-scale.

After experiments, the surfactant activity of the dialyzed and lyophilized biosurfactant extracts was assessed by surface tension (ST) measurements using a Krüss K20 EasyDyne tensiometer with a 1.9 cm platinum Wilhelmy plate (Krüss GmbH, Hamburg, Germany). Additionally, the critical micellar concentration (CMC) was determined starting with a concentration of 1 g/L and performing several dilutions in deionized water. All measurements were carried out in triplicate (Rodríguez-López et al., 2020).

An elemental analyzer (Fisons Carlo Erba EA-1108 CHNS-O, LabX, Midland, ON, Canada) was also used to determine the content of C, H, N, and S in the dialyzed and lyophilized biosurfactant extracts. All determinations were performed in triplicate (Rodríguez-López et al., 2020). The percentage of nitrogen (N) was used to calculate the protein content, following the procedure described by Mariotti et al. (2008).

Finally, infrared spectroscopy analysis of the dialyzed and lyophilized biosurfactant extracts was performed using a Nicolet 6700 FTIR system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) in ATR mode. The spectra were recorded with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in a wavenumber range from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹, with an average of 32 scans (Martínez-Arcos et al., 2024). The degree of similarity between the biosurfactant extracts was calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r_p) from the spectral measurements taken in transmittance mode, using the Excel statistical tool (Henschel et al., 2020; Martínez-Arcos et al., 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the Pearson's coefficient, it can be observed that the biosurfactant extracts of dialysis processes at both scales are similar, with a calculated r_p of 0.92. In addition, **Table 1** shows the surfactant activity and elemental analysis data of the biosurfactant extracts obtained after the dialysis processes of CSW, at lab and pilot scale, respectively. All data represent the mean value and standard deviation of three determinations. According, the t -text ($p=0.05$ or $p=0.01$) for pairwise comparison, both biosurfactant extract present similar Min ST values, however significant differences were found for their CMC and elemental analysis data. In general, the biosurfactant extract obtained by lab-scale shows higher values of N, proteins, C and S than those obtained when using the pilot-scale process, while for the content of H occurs the opposite. In addition, the lab-scale biosurfactant extract present a more favourable CMC value (0.074 g/L) regarding that obtained with pilot-scale system (0.12 g/L). Overall, these biosurfactant extracts are yellowish powders that can reduce surface tension of water by 20 units and have a CMC values ranged from 0.074-0.12 g/L.

Table 1. Characteristics of the biosurfactant extracts recovered by dialysis processes at lab and pilot scale.

	Lab-scale	Pilot-scale	
Appearance			
			<i>t</i> -Test <i>t</i> Value*
Min ST (mN/m)	52.20 ± 0.20 ^a	54.43 ± 1.17 ^a	1.550
CMC (g/L)	0.074 ± 0.002 ^a	0.12 ± 0.01 ^b	7.813
N (%)	8.35 ± 0.07 ^a	6.51 ± 0.05 ^b	-37.05
Protein (%)	52.16 ± 0.41 ^a	40.66 ± 0.31 ^b	38.75
C (%)	35.16 ± 0.13 ^a	33.24 ± 0.13 ^b	-18.09
H (%)	5.47 ± 0.10 ^a	6.06 ± 0.08 ^b	7.980
S (%)	1.14 ± 0.03 ^a	0.44 ± 0.06 ^b	18.07

Min ST = minimum surface tension; CMC = critical micellar concentration; N = nitrogen; Protein = was calculated by multiplying the nitrogen content by 6.25 (Mariotti et al. 2008); C = carbon; H = hydrogen; S = sulfur. Different Latin letters for the same variable indicate significant differences between the lab-scale and pilot-scale dialysis processes.

* $t_{critical} = 2.776$ ($p = 0.05$ and 4 degrees of freedom); $t_{critical} = 4.604$ ($p = 0.01$ and 4 degrees of freedom).

When comparing these biosurfactant extracts with the biosurfactant extracted from CSW by other processes, such as liquid-liquid extractions using organic solvents, they show different characteristics: a powdery appearance instead of an oily one, a lower reduction in water surface tension (around 20 units instead of 30 units), a lower CMC (0.07-0.12 g/L instead of 0.15-0.18 g/L), and a higher percentage of nitrogen (6.51-8.35% instead of 1.08-1.32%) (Vecino et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

The dialysis process has demonstrated to be an efficient and sustainable process for recovering biosurfactants from corn steep water without using organic solvents. Furthermore, the ATEMBIO project successfully advanced the TRL of the membrane technology to levels 4-6. No significant differences were observed for minimum ST between the biosurfactant extracts obtained at lab-scale and those recovered at pilot-scale. In contrast, significant differences were found in CMC values and elemental analysis, although these differences would not substantially affect the surfactant

activity of the two compared extracts. Additionally, to explore potential industrial applications of these biosurfactant extracts, further studies on their composition and properties are required.

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